

CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the specific characteristics of verbs in English and Uzbek languages from a scientific and practical point of view. During the analysis, the specific features of the verbs of the two languages, the place of auxiliary verbs and independent verbs in the sentence, suffixes and affixes added to verbs as well as definite and indefinite forms of the verb were studied.*

Keywords: *verb, action, case, suffix, prefixes, tense, form, inclination, proportion, lexicon, characteristics.*

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ГЛАГОЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *В статье анализируются специфические характеристики глаголов в английском и узбекском языках с научной и практической точки зрения. В ходе анализа изучались особенности глаголов двух языков, место в предложении вспомогательных глаголов и самостоятельных глаголов, суффиксы и аффиксы, присоединяемые к глаголам, а также определенные и неопределенные формы глагола. статье анализируются специфические характеристики глаголов в английском и узбекском языках.*

Ключевые слова: *глагол, действие, падеж, суффикс, префиксы, время, форма, наклонение, пропорция, лексика, характеристика.*

INTRODUCTION

We know that in linguistics, the verb is the main part of the sentence. Every sentence cannot be without a verb, that is, without a participle. It follows naturally that the study of verb phrase is an important factor, and much research is currently being conducted in this regard.

The analysis shows that English and Uzbek verbs are relatively similar, but differ only in terms of the place they are used in the sentence. However, the characteristics of verbs in these two languages have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, it is important to carry out scientific practical research on the analysis and justification of the features, differences and common aspects of the verb word group in the Uzbek and English languages.

Literature analysis. In the course of the analysis conducted that in English, the characteristics of the verb are gerund and infinitive forms, while in Uzbek they are similar to the form of the verb that is only the name of the action [2, 355].

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The verb word group and its characteristics in Uzbek and English languages were taken as the research object. The analysis of the processes of learning the characteristics of the verb phrase in English and Uzbek was carried out according to the literature related to the subject and the results of previous scientific works.

According to the results of scientific theoretical studies, about the verb, we can say without any extra similes that the verb is an independent group of words and expresses an action and state or process. We can characterize the verb as an independent word group based on the following characteristics:

1. According to the lexical grammatical meaning as action and state or process;

2. According to the possession of unique stem-forming suffixes and prefixes and lexical grammatical word morphemes;

3. Due to the fact that the verb has more grammatical categories than other word groups, it is more developed in terms of word formation and modification than other word groups;

4. According to the way verbs are connected in their own way;

5. According to the fact that it can appear in any syntactic function in the sentence.

A verb is a group of words that expresses an action-state or process and has aspect, tense, inclination, ratio, perfect, modality and other such grammatical categories.

Verbs in the Uzbek language are divided into independent verbs and auxiliary verbs according to their lexical-grammatical characteristics. Independent verbs indicate action, have an independent meaning and can act as a part of a sentence.

For example: Hadicha poured water on the flowers in the garden.

Hadicha bog'dagi gullarga suv quydi.

Independent verbs in the Uzbek language, as well as in the English language, have the following forms: pure verb, noun of action, adjective, adverb, depending on the specific task of the word group.

Auxiliary verbs are used in various grammatical expressions and other tasks. We can also divide auxiliary verbs into the following types according to several characteristics:

1. auxiliary verbs that serve to form words and act as linking verbs;

2. verbs combining with verbs and expressing different joint meanings.

In both languages, verbs are a group of words that mainly indicate the activity of a person.

We can see this from the following examples:

For instance: John and Ann are coming to market.

He wants to graduate from university with honors.

U universitetni a'lo baholarga tamomlamoqchi.

Verbs in English and Uzbek languages (in any language) can be divided into simple, passive, compound verbs according to their morphological structure, like other word groups.

Verbs that consist of a simple stem and do not have any suffix in the verb are considered simple verbs.

For example:

In Uzbek: kelmoq, yozmoq, yubormoq.

In English: to come, to write, to send.

Passive verbs are formed by adding verb-forming additions and suffixes to words from other word groups.

For example:

In Uzbek: **-lan** ovqatlanmoq;

-lash suhbatlashmoq.

In English: **-dis** disappoint;

-re rewrite.

It should also be added that in Uzbek you can make a new verb from words that are not verbs. That is, a verb cannot be made from a verb. In English, such a phenomenon is not observed, that is, a verb can be made from a verb [7, 7-10].

For example, in Uzbek, you can say **-la gulla**, but not *borla*.

In English: **-dis** disappear;

-re restart.

Compound verbs are made up of two or more stems.

For example:

In Uzbek: sotib olmoq, kirib chiqmoq.

In English: to whitewash, to broadcast.

In addition, verbs can be formed in the form of verb + adverb.

For example: to take off - yechmoq,

to go on - davom etmoq.

In English, there are definite and indefinite forms of the verb, which differ from each other according to whether they are accented or not in the sentence. Forms of verbs that change in the categories of person, number, tense, tense and can act as participles in a sentence are called Finite Forms of the Verbs, that is, predicative forms [6, 112].

For example: John asked me.

Forms of the verb that show the action and state in general and show a partial character or subjectivity are called non-finite forms of the verb, i.e. non-predicative forms.

RESEARCH RESULTS

According to the results of the analysis, these forms are formed differently in the Uzbek and English languages. According to the analysis, in English, if the verb is preceded by "to" or the suffix "-ing" is added to the end of the verb, it is formed by the suffixes "-ish, -moq" in Uzbek. We can see such analytical results not only in the verb form, but also in several verb characteristics. They are all mentioned above section.

DISCUSSION

As can be seen from the above examples, the verbs in Uzbek and English are different according to their characteristics. We can see such differences in the place of use of the verb in the sentence, suffixes and prefixes, verb forms, the use of auxiliary and independent verbs, the function of the verb in the sentence, compound and simple verbs, and several similar features.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it should be said that in both languages, i.e., in English and in Uzbek, verbs differ from other groups of words according to their morphological, lexical-semantic, lexical-grammatical characteristics. As stated by Boronov, the verb reflects the specific characteristics of the action that takes place during a certain period of time [1, 283]. These features are manifested in the personal forms of the verb, since the syntactic function of the personal forms of the verb is only participle in the sentence.

REFERENCES

1. Boronov J.B. Comparative grammar of English and Uzbek languages. Publisher. - T.: Teacher, 1973. -283 p.
2. G'apparov M. "English Grammar", -T.: Turon-Iqbal, 2006. -355 p.
3. Jumayeva, Mukarrama Bekzodovna (2022). OLIY TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION USUL VA VOSITALAR. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (Special Issue 20), 214-226. doi: 10.24412/2181-1784-2022-20-214-226.
4. Maxmudjonov Ibroximjon, & Jumayeva Mukarrama. (2022). HOZIRGI KUN YOSHLARINI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA KIRISHISHIDA CHET

TILLARINI O'RGATILISHI VA UNING AHAMIYATI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(5), 178–182.

5. Mukarrama, J., Jasurbek, A., & Kamoliddin, S. (2022). Обучение навыкам аудирования на английском языке. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(6), 1-4.
6. Ne'matov H, Mahmudov N, Saifullayeva R, G'ulomov A, Abduraimova M. Mother tongue. Textbook for 8th grade. -Tashkent, 2002.-112 p.
7. Talibov Begzod Furqatzoda "Copulative verbs in English and Uzbek" Samarkand-2012 pp. 7-10.